

VALUABLE

VALORISATION OF FUNGAL BIOMASS USING NOVEL ENZYMATIC TECHNOLOGY

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Deliverable Title	Chemically produced chitin
Work Package No.	WP2
Work Package Title	<i>A. niger</i> biomass treatment & chitin extraction
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public (PU) / <input type="checkbox"/> Sensitive (SEN)
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